

SURVEY – TOOLS SUPPORTING OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH AND SAFETY (OHS) IN THE POLISH CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY

We kindly ask you to carefully complete the following survey. The few minutes you spend on this will significantly influence the direction of further research aimed at developing tools and methods to support the work of those involved in OHS.

The survey is addressed to people who deal with OHS issues in their professional work and is completely anonymous (average time to complete the survey - approximately 5 minutes).

PRELIMINARY INFORMATION

1. Year of birth:

2. Gender: female male I refuse to answer

3. Province(s):
(Please indicate all the provinces in which you currently work)

4. Professional experience in the field of OHS (in years):

5. Current position:

- OHS inspector senior OHS inspector
 OHS specialist senior OHS specialist
 chief OHS specialist other:.....

6. What is the ownership structure of the company where you currently work?

- Private company State-owned company Self-employed

7. Number of people employed in the company where you currently work:

- 1 person (self-employed) 2-9 persons 10-49 persons
 50-249 persons 250-499 persons over 500 persons
 other:.....

WORK TIME ANALYSIS

8. How much time do you spend on the following tasks during an average working week?

(Average working week – standard period of work in a week, which usually comprises 40 hours of work spread over five working days)

Name of task	Average number of hours spent during an average working week					
	No more than 1 hour	1 – 3 hours	3 – 5 hours	5 – 8 hours	8 hours and more	Not applicable/ no opinion
Communication (including e-mails, phone calls)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Analysis and review of documentation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Preparation of documentation and reports	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Participation in training courses (as a participant)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Conducting OHS training	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Participation in meetings (e.g. construction meetings, OHS meetings)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
OHS inspection of workstations	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Self-education, including learning how to use software	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other tasks that you perform during an average working week that are not listed above	No. 1.....	<input type="checkbox"/>				
	No. 2	<input type="checkbox"/>				
	No. 3	<input type="checkbox"/>				

USE OF TECHNOLOGY IN EVERYDAY WORK

10. What software do you currently use to support your daily work?

Office suite, e.g. MS Office (including Word, Excel, PowerPoint, Outlook) or similar

Risk management software – which one? *(Please specify)*

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Software for preparing reports/documentation – which ones? *(Please specify)*

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Error identification software – which one? *(Please specify)*

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Software for simulating phenomena – what kind? *(Please specify)*

(e.g. software for simulating the spread of fire or hazardous substances; virtual reality (VR) simulation software, etc.)

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Other technologies/solutions supporting everyday work – what kind? *(Please specify)*

(e.g. individual macros or scripts; artificial intelligence (AI) solutions – e.g. Chat GPT (OpenAI), Gemini (Google); others)

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11. What is your attitude towards the use of modern technologies in your daily work? *(Please rate each statement on the scale below)*

Task name	Strongly agree	Agree	Partially agree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
I am someone who has no reservations about using new technologies in my daily work.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I always or almost always use the latest version of the software	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I often test new technologies/software	<input type="checkbox"/>				

I am someone who uses new technologies/ software only when necessary	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I consider myself to be someone who uses new technologies/software more often than other people in my immediate environment or workplace.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I am a person who is interested in the development of new technologies/software	<input type="checkbox"/>				

12. Are there any processes in your work that you think could be automated or supported by new technologies to improve your daily work?

- No
- Yes – which ones? *(Please list and briefly describe them)*

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